

PRAGMALINGUISTIC FUNCTIONAL- METHODOLOGICAL CLASSIFICATION OF EUPHEMISM

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Abstract

Euphemism is an important linguistic unit in humans speech. It has been researched by it's structural historical and linguistical side many times but there are not enough information that will hold a survey by it's pragmatistical aspects . Pragmalinguistics or pragmatics is a huge branch of modern linguistics and has a huge impact on modern linguistics. Modern linguistics is also a branch of general linguistics. While other field of linguistics study language by it's consistence , structure, history, function modern linguistic fields study it through humans who are using this language. So it is something individual gives euphemism another meaningful aspect. In this article you will be informed about progmalingual side of euphemism especially through maxims

Key words

Linguistics, Pragmatics, pragma linguistics, maxsima, semiotics , implication

The most prominent branch of modern linguistics is pragmatics or pragmalinguistics. Pragmatics is the branch of linguistics concerned with what the speaker means and what the listener infers based on factors such as the context of the situation, the mental state of the individuals, previous dialogue, and other elements. In linguistics (the study of language), pragmatics is a special branch of science that focuses on the relationship between natural language and its users. Pragmatics focuses on the effects of speech, or what the speaker means and what the hearer infers. To define pragmatics, scholars sometimes compare and contrast it with linguistic semantics (the meaning of a sentence) or contrast it with syntax (word order) or semiotics (the study of signs), all of which are separate terms. Historically, pragmatics dates back to antiquity, when rhetoric was one of the three liberal arts. The more modern idea of pragmatics emerged in England, France, and Germany in the 1780s and 1830s. Pragmatism gained popularity between 1880 and 1930 when linguists studying the philosophy of language agreed that language should be studied in the context of communication and life, and that language itself is a type of human activity. Today, linguistics is a multidisciplinary research field that includes natural sciences, social sciences, and humanities.

People often associate pragmatics with other areas of linguistics, such as semantics, syntax, and semiotics, but these terms have different definitions. Semantics is a science that studies the systems of rules that determine the literal linguistic meanings of expressions; syntax describes how we put words together to make meaningful sentences; Semiotics, on the other hand, deals with the use and interpretation of signs and symbols.

Unlike semantics, syntax, and semiotics, the study of pragmatics revolves around the literal and nonliteral aspects of language and how physical or social contexts determine the use of these linguistic expressions. Pragmatics is an important branch of English linguistics. It helps us look beyond the literal meaning of words and phrases and allows us to focus on how meaning is constructed in a particular context. When communicating with other people, there is a constant negotiation of meaning between the listener and the speaker. Pragmatics looks at this negotiation and seeks to understand what people mean when they communicate with each other.

Before looking more specifically at examples of the linguistic field of pragmatics, let's get acquainted with the term "pragmatics".

Pragmatics examines the difference between the literal meaning of words and their intended meaning in a social context. It takes into account things like irony, metaphor, and intention.

The Oxford Companion to Philosophy (1995) defines pragmatics as:

"Language study that focuses on users and the context of language use rather than on reference, truth, or grammar"

Since pragmatics is a branch of linguistics, there is no direct synonym for this term. There are different aspects of pragmatics, such as implied meaning and speech acts. These aspects are important in understanding the field of pragmatics in general.

As you can see, euphemisms and pragmatics are very close concepts. Because as the research object of pragmalinguistics, phenomena such as meaning, hidden meaning, and implication are understood, any euphemism is widely used to express another by one word.

The definition of the subject of linguistic pragmatics causes many difficulties. It is often succinctly defined as the science that seeks to describe language not in its internal, immanent structure, but in its human use [6]. In addition, according to V.V. Bogdanov, the subject of studying pragmatics includes the rules and conventions of speech behavior accepted in a certain society, along with other rules of language use by communicants in acts of speech communication. according to [6]. As K. Ya. Segal wrote, "the field of linguistic pragmatics, which includes the theory of speech acts as an integral part, covers the study of the communicative function (and specific communicative functions) of language units in their conscious context. the use of the speaker in speech activity to fulfill his communicative semantic task and to control the speech and non-speech actions of the addressee" [5, p. 88]. To understand the connection between euphemism and pragmatics, the euphemism formulated by M. L. Kovshova is We give the definition: "A euphemism is a word or phrase that replaces those words or phrases according to the speaker's opinion and accordingly. following the rules of speech etiquette, it is undesirable, does not meet the goals of communication and can lead to communicative failure" [2, p. 7]. Pragmatic approach to euphemism is due to the fact that the use of euphemisms arises from the requirements of norms of speech behavior. Thus and O. S. Sakhno considers euphemism to be a traditional form of speech activity aimed at implicitly defining denotations [4, p. 9]. According to E. G. Borisova and Yu. S. Martemyanov, "the speaker and the listener are a wordless euphemistic "conspiracy" enters: the speaker consciously encodes the meaning, hides it, offers it to the listener in the form of a euphemism, and the listener decodes the meaning by performing a

series of speech-thinking operations. According to point 2, p. 44]. E' note that the speaker decodes the meaning taking into account the context and background knowledge. As L.P. Krisin wrote, the desire to avoid communicative discomfort by changing the way euphemisms express an unpleasant fact is a special case of the implementation of the postulate of politeness formulated by P. Gris [3, p. 270]. Therefore, the use of euphemisms allows you to remove the emotional tension caused by the conflict between the speaker's desire to designate directly and the prohibition of using this sign. Euphemism is characterized by precision, that is, by not formally expressing the pragmatic information it contains. The implicit meaning of a euphemism corresponds to the illocutionary meaning of the sentence associated with the euphemism. The illocutionary component consists in the conscious creation of a mitigating substitute for words or phrases that, in the opinion of the speaker, are unpleasant or rude to the interlocutor. However, when decoding the indirect nomination, that is, the euphemism, and restoring the denotation, the implicature in them is simultaneously evident. The perlocutionary component or effect result is the beneficial effect of soft speech on the interlocutor, the emotional rapprochement between the interlocutors, and the effect of successful communication in general. 36–37].

As can be seen from the above, euphemism, which is a speech act, has all the components of speech acts: location - the actual pronunciation of a statement, illocution - intentional orientation and perlocution - the result of influence [2, p. 35]. In addition, euphemism is characterized by conditionality as a symbolic tool. Thus, in the pragmatic aspect, euphemism is a flexible mechanism that allows for the regulation of the relationship between the speaker and reality, where various stigmatized concepts often become the object of reference, that is, complex and unpleasant feelings. engendering concepts.

The study of euphemisms is found in sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, cognitive linguistics and speech pragmatics. This makes it possible to distinguish the following main directions of research: socio-cultural (L. P. Krisin, V. P. Moskvina, B. A. Larin), psychological (A. S. Kurkova, V. P. Moskvina, M. S. Retunskaya, V. Yu. Kharitonova), pragmatic (T. M. Abakova, T. S. Bushueva, N. A. Vanyushina, K. Allan, K. Burrige) and related linguistics (N. M. Berdov, A. M. Prudivus, N. V. Pryadilnikova, N. M. Potapova, etc.). Euphemisms are pragmatically defined units [8]. Due to their effect, the euphemisms of the addressee's speech are pragmatic opposites. Using these language units is a means of implementing speech pragmatics. The formation of euphemisms is related to the pragmatic principle of politeness. The functions of euphemisms include manipulation, veiling, self-defense; has functions. First of all, it should be noted that the pragmatic aspect of the meaning is an integral part of the linguistic unit, which includes both the indication of the given name and the specific communicative situation (formal - neutral - informal). In the semantics of a language unit, the sign of this is the register in which it mainly operates. In each communicative register, in each social group, and in each of them, a separate regional version of the language has its own euphemisms, a fact created on the basis of the general need to cover various phenomena. Euphemistic words or expressions are able to hide facts and events, to have a deliberately unfavorable rating system in the public mind, and to arouse antipathy. The linguistic nature of euphemisms is expressed by the fact that they distract the attention of the recipient from the forbidden concept and are thus considered emotionally neutral substitutes for such, unwanted or very harsh labels.

Consider the main functional types of euphemisms: - It has long been noted that euphemisms can be used to replace "Specific names of distinguished things and events" [5, p. 51]. For example, nouns can also become the object of euphemism for some diseases that lead to death: "neoplasm", "new growth" (tumor) instead of "cancroid" (cancer), but in this example Shuni ta It should be noted that the word "cancroid" is a direct name for skin cancer, which today requires replacement with euphemisms.

- Euphemisms are used when one does not want to directly name something unpleasant or disgusting. For example, instead of words, insects are directly called parasites: "lice", "mite", "flea". descriptive and indirect nouns: "pest" (parasite), "insect".

- In a certain period and when a certain society is considered indecent, it is spoken euphemistically. B. A. Larin believes that euphemisms are called household, because euphemisms for this category are characterized by a limited range of ideas in the fields of physiology and science. human anatomy, as well as their function mainly in spoken speech [3, p. 113].

- Euphemisms about manners. This type of euphemism is used when the speaker avoids giving a direct name for fear of offending the interlocutor. IN In this case, it is necessary to replace words that are quite appropriate, but from the point of view of the speaker, they are worried about insulting the people they are addressing.

- A layer of euphemisms is very important for masking or disguising the real essence of what is indicated [1, p.590]. Various "disguising" euphemisms are political euphemisms, the purpose of which is to deceive public opinion and express something more subtly unpleasant.

- Euphemisms are used to indicate professions and organizations that are not prestigious in a certain society. In modern English, the class of euphemisms with the function of language is very important "work to raise the status of unskilled and unskilled occupations" [7, p. 357]. For example: "sanitary engineer" (sanitary engineer) instead of "waste reduction manager" (builder) "Building maintenance engineer" and "home maintenance engineer" instead of "janitor" is used instead of the word

It should be remembered that there is a complex relationship between semantics and pragmatics. Dialectical connection is a kind of diffusion. Thus, according to the understanding of J. Leach, Semantics means meaning, and pragmatics means the power of impact on the receiver [10, p. 17].

Leech, G. N. introduced pragmatic principles in his work "Principle of Pragmatics", he said that pragmatic principles can be divided into two classes: the principle of cooperation and the principle of politeness. (Leech, 1983)

In 1985, DJ Enright published a collection of essays entitled "Fair of Speech, the Use of Euphemism". collected many essays on euphemism and provided information for future euphemistic studies. In 1991, Allan Keith Burrige published the book Euphemism and Dysphimism, which is very useful for scholars who read the book. a pragmatic study of English euphemism. Burrige proposed that a euphemism is a word that is pleasant or offensive, or a term used to replace obscenities, blasphemies, or taboos. Various types of euphemisms are also found in the Bible. (Burbidge, 1991) In 2003 Wierzebecka, A. published Cross-Cultural Pragmatics: The Semantics of Human Interaction. This work was about the principles used in human interaction. He suggested that pragmatics can be used as a guide to human beings (Wierzebecka, 2003). The American scholar Hugh Rawson once said that

euphemisms are so deeply embedded in our language that none of us can go a day without euphemisms, not even ourselves. both those who claim directly and suggest that he uses euphemisms. (Hugh, 1981)

Pragmatic principles refer to the principle of cooperation and the principle of politeness. In real communication, people use pragmatic principles to guide their daily lives. Euphemism is a common phenomenon in the history of human beings and it is expressed euphemistically in different language communities and for some at different social levels. and In real life, people use euphemistic, elegant, polite words instead of apostate, hurtful, rude words to make each other feel comfortable and harmless. not difficult. Pragmatic principles are used to guide people's communication activities, so pragmatic principles play a leading role in the use of certain euphemisms.

For example, the tact maxim of the principle of courtesy: minimize harm to others and maximize benefit. For example, can you lend me your watch? That is, when talking to people, you need to be strategic. Minimize harm to others and maximize benefits. If you want to lend a watch, you say, "Would you..." This makes people feel comfortable and makes them feel that you are a polite person, and the levels of compliance will be higher. Using this phrase makes the sentence euphemistic. That is, under the guidance of the maxim of tact, people express their thoughts more euphemistically. In short, pragmatic principles are guidelines for the use of euphemisms.

Conclusion

Pragmalinguistics and euphemization is very interconnected . Because pragmatics refering intended meaning by other words and euphemism also tend to rename word to more intended version of it. Actually, In the sentances where people use euphemism mostly there are pragmatics and this is usual thing.

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